

Design Report: Volunteer Spotlight

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Design Report Analysis: Volunteer Spotlight

Introduction

In this project, we were tasked with creating a way that people can express their gratitude through technology, and have designed a mobile application that can serve as both a platform for connecting people through good news and helping them to serve their community. Our app, Volunteer Spotlight, will serve as a platform for volunteer organisations to post “spotlight” stories on volunteers they are grateful for. In spreading their stories, the aim of this platform is to also provide those interested with ways to connect to potential volunteer organisations, as well as provide them with a way to share gratitude of their own in the form of well-wishes and donations to these charities.

Design Brief

Background

When thinking about this design opportunity, our group thought first of what it meant to be grateful and to show gratitude. We determined that, for our intents and purposes, gratitude would mean “how beneficiaries express their gratitude and may reciprocate to benefactors” (Mendoca, Mercon-Vargas, & Tudge, 2017). Volunteerism can be thought of as an act of gratitude in physical form. For all that volunteers do for our society, it would be nice to find a way to give a little bit of that back to them and show them how much we as society members are grateful for their contributions.

Design Opportunity

The idea of the “Volunteer Spotlight” thus came from the identification of a need for recognition of the many volunteers that go under-appreciated, and a desire to show just how much they are appreciated. Through the data we collected, we demonstrate in this project that an app designed to show gratitude for volunteers is not only necessary but important in the sense that it will allow society to give a little gratitude back to the volunteers that work so hard to improve the lives of those around them.

Research and Requirements Gathering

A brief review of literature

Why do individuals volunteer? Volunteers don't expect to get paid in kind for their efforts. Thus, there should be a strong incentive for people to give their time and effort to others. Snyder and Omoto (2008) considered volunteering as a general 'social action' when people are trying to tackle common issues in society. There are several reasons why people volunteer. While some of them could be self-motivated (career development, improvement of self-esteem or social interactions), others include following positive agendas personally or as a part of a bigger social group. On a personal level, some particular personal characteristics, such as empathy, could make people more likely to volunteer (Snyder and Omoto, 2008).

Why do people continue to volunteer? Snyder and Omoto (2008) suggested that people evaluate volunteering from two sides: personal satisfaction and other people's perception of their work. From a personal perspective, Grant (2007) considered that people put more time and effort into their work when they have a chance to see a beneficial impact on their beneficiaries. Hence, a clear connection between acts and the beneficial effects they have on others could motivate volunteers to continue their work.

From other people's perceptions, it is important for volunteers to feel that their work is important (Snyder and Omoto, 2008). So, showing appreciation and gratitude for them could keep them volunteering. Doing so could not only motivate the ones who are already volunteering but also inspires other people to join these organisations.

Volunteering influences people in many ways. They make new social relationships, gain knowledge and experience changes in attitude and health (Snyder and Omoto, 2008). Those changes could be both positive and stressful, depending on the circumstances. However, Ghandeharioun (2016) has shown a strong relationship between appreciation and both psychological and physical health. People who are grateful are said to feel happier and more upbeat, to be better able to cope with negative circumstances and to have closer relationships with others. Both individuals who receive assistance and those who give it gain from volunteering.

Process and results of user engagement

Choosing the user group

The main goals of our platform are showing gratitude to volunteers by spreading information about their achievements and helping people to find suitable volunteer opportunities. Thus, our target user group is adults generally interested in volunteering independently of their personal or professional background.

Process

To conduct an early-stage validation of the idea, we decided to conduct both qualitative and quantitative research through a survey. As stated by Klein, surveys are a great way to reach a large number of people (Klein, 2018). To understand user perspectives and pain points, a 15 point questionnaire survey was conducted. The questions were a blend of personal questions and questions related to the user's take on gratitude and volunteer work (see Figure A.1 in [Appendix A](#)). We received 72 responses overall. The key findings are listed below:

- 79% of responders were 18 to 30 years old (31-45 - 13%, 46-65 - 6%, over 65 - 3%).
- 86% of responders were interested in volunteering.
- 71% of responders had volunteered in the past.
- 57% of responders who had not volunteered in the past, were interested in volunteering in the future.
- 60% of responders think that voluntary work does not receive enough recognition.
- 89% of responders are interested in reading stories about people who help others (answered 'Yes' - 56%, 'Maybe' - 33%).
- 93% could potentially visit a website to read stories about people who help others (10% - very likely, 36% - likely, 47% - somewhat likely, 4% - unlikely, 3% - not likely).

To summarise the primary research conducted, most of the respondents felt voluntary work does not receive enough recognition and gratitude. Lack of inaction with volunteer groups and their work often makes a volunteer look more like a hobbyist and their efforts go unnoticed. As a token of gratitude, most of the respondents wished to read more volunteer stories and turn gratitude into action by volunteering to work for various causes or making donations to support a good cause.

Secondary Research

Currently, over 1 billion people worldwide volunteer at some capacity, either in their local communities or globally for nonprofit organisations (TeamStage, 2022). According to a study done in 2017, 75% of working millennials reported that they would volunteer more if they had a better understanding of the organisations that they could volunteer with and how their work would make a difference (Deloitte, 2017).

Based on a study published by Nonprofit Tech For Good, there is a wide spread of interests when it comes to volunteer opportunities (2022). When looking at the differing causes that are most popular in each continent, it is easy to see that there is a wide range of interests, and that one type of volunteer work in one part of the world will be vastly different in another part. Also, the way that people volunteer is different, as many countries show that online donations are the most popular in their region, whereas in-person volunteering is more popular in others (Nonprofit Tech For Good, 2022).

Accessibility Considerations

To build an equitable platform, we are following the Web Accessibility Initiative guidelines (World Wide Web Consortium, 2019) for accessibility and considered adding the following:

Use of plain language: The platform uses plain language, simple sentence structures and avoids the use of jargons to make it more convenient for a global audience and to ensure non-english speakers are not left out confused.

Colour contrast: We have considered text and background colour contrast to ensure that people with low visibility or colour blindness don't struggle to read text.

Font size: The text, images and clickable buttons are large enough and follow Web Accessibility Initiative guidelines.

Personas

According to Miaskiewicz and Kozar, personas can help improve the overall design of a product by putting a focus on user goals, which can lead to a more specialised feature set and guide decision-making (2011). Based on the data, we knew our user group would be mostly young users between the ages of 18-30, and with varied interests in volunteering.

Our first persona, Sean O'Malley (see Figure A.2 and A.3 in [Appendix A](#)), was based here in Dublin because a large number of respondents were based in Ireland. He fits into the age demographic, has an extensive background with volunteer work, and even helps with the running of a local volunteer organisation. Sean is interested in using our platform as a fun way to thank fellow volunteers in his favourite organisation. With a full-time job, Sean is busy, and does not have time for an overly-complicated product design.

Our other persona, Jake Smith (see Figure A.4 and A.5 in [Appendix A](#)), is a very young user based in America. As a college student, his main goal is to use our platform to accomplish a task, mainly finding a volunteer opportunity to fulfil a scholarship. He does not have access to a car and as such, needs opportunities that are walking distance to his campus. He is interested in animal volunteer activities, and wants to choose something he can do with friends.

These personas represent two different motivations: “task based” – mainly those who will use our platform to find volunteer opportunities – and “value-based” – who use the platform for sentiment (Berger et al., 2022). In the work by Zellhoffer, the importance of covering all possible utilities of a user group is necessary in the creation of personas, as that will inspire better problem solving in the scenario process with actual user behaviour (2014). This difference in behaviour requirements will help us as we begin to explore scenarios with the two personas.

Blue Ocean Strategy (Competitive Audit)

According to Levy (2021), conducting market research on the competition is a crucial component of business strategy to gain firsthand knowledge of the good and bad user experiences provided by the competitors. Following recommendations of (Czepiel & Kerin, 2012) we conducted the competitive audit to understand the direct and indirect competitors of the ‘Volunteer Spotlight’ platform and study their strengths and weaknesses. Understanding where to fit these successful features in the ‘Volunteer Spotlight’ platform will help us in the early stage of the design process.

Volunteer Ireland: we found that ‘Volunteer Ireland’ is a direct competitor platform and caters to volunteering enthusiasts, corporate and non-profit organisations. They share volunteer stories, provide a platform for volunteer recruitment, volunteer training, support and resources to various volunteer organisations.

VolunteerMatch: it is a platform to promote voluntary activities by posting volunteer requirements for interested volunteers with a good number of volunteer organisations involved. The platform has various volunteer categories such as animals, art, culture and technology which makes it easier for the users to find the voluntary work of their interest.

Humans of New York: it is an indirect competitor and they employ unique ways to display their gratitude towards voluntary work by sharing volunteer stories. The platform maintains a consistent theme, which is an add-on to the good user experience.

The competitors have used the latest available features on mobile phones and desktops to enhance user experience such as visual designs, strong branding, etc. Platforms have great features to support voluntary work and various volunteer organisations, but they have some issues too. Such as: complex user interfaces; lack of engaging user design, convenience to find

suitable activities and show gratitude to volunteers. Figure B.1 (see [Appendix B](#)) summarises our competitive audit findings.

User Journey Map and Problem Tree

User journey map visually represents the user experience using a product or service (Howard, 2014). We decided to apply our persona Jake Smith to understand the current user experience. Rather than only apply it to the service, we described the whole volunteering process to gain better insights about users' real goals, from finding nearby animal shelter volunteer opportunities to real-world activities (Stickdorn et al., 2018). We described the stages and steps of interaction, touchpoints, stakeholders and emotions in Figure B.2 (see [Appendix B](#)). During this stage, we found several problems which users could experience during the process, such as lack of information and its clarity, difficulties in finding suitable opportunities, the high level of time demand for that search, lack of resources for volunteer organisations etc. Figure B.3 (see [Appendix B](#)) shows a problem tree generated from found problems, brainstormed causes and offerings to tackle those issues.

Choosing an interface

Our platform needed two main functions: the ability to spread volunteer stories and easily find information and communicate with volunteer organisations. Sharp et al. (2019) suggest that identified requirements should dictate the appropriate interface. Thus, a mobile application is the most appropriate interface to reach diverse users, keep them engaged with volunteer stories and easily communicate with volunteer organisations.

Design Concepts

As a result of the research and requirements gathering stage, we decided to design a mobile application where people can see inspiring volunteer stories and all the necessary information about volunteer organisations. The application map shows organisations, activities and stories to help users choose which suits them. Potential volunteers can choose suitable opportunities and communicate with host organisations. By spreading (posting, liking and sharing) volunteer stories, both organisations and users not only show gratitude for volunteers and their work but also gain positive effects for themselves.

Creative Design and Lo-Fi Prototypes

Creative Design

Design ideas and idea generation

Following Sharp et al. (2019) suggestions, we run a brainstorming session to develop unique design ideas. The resulting Figure C.1 (see [Appendix C](#)) shows all the ideas generated during the session (features to include, issues to solve). Categorised these ideas into three groups (see Figure C.2 in [Appendix C](#)), we exposed two main features: a map of organisations and activities and a map of stories. Thus, we decided to use those core features for two alternative design ideas: map-based and story-based.

Lo-fi Prototypes

As Walker et al. (2002) recommended we chose digital wireframes for our low-fidelity prototypes based on practical considerations. While using Adobe XD software to make lo-fi prototypes, it is much easier to transform the result into a hi-fi prototype eventually. Moreover, such computer prototypes help to understand the concept and provide more feedback about it (Walker et al., 2002).

Lo-fi 1: the map prototype

The first prototype (see Figure C.3 in [Appendix C](#)) is map focused. The ‘Volunteer’ tab on the main page shows the volunteer organisations on the map by default. Users could choose Icons of specific geographic areas to check organisations worldwide. Users can filter by organisation type - so only required information will be shown. Tapping on an organisation icon, users see its page with a list of current activities. Each activity has its page with specific information.

The ‘Story’ tab has the same map logic, but users can see geographically specific stories. Each story has a link to volunteer activity information.

The bar at the bottom of the screen has four options:

- ‘Map’ - as described above.
- ‘Volunteer’ tab shows a list of all volunteer activities nearby and a list of applied ones by a user.
- ‘Message’ tab shows messages and contacts.
- ‘Me’ - user information.

By tapping on the ‘+’ icon on the main screen, users can add a story (by choosing appropriate content on the first page and text on the second).

Lo-fi 2: the stories prototype

The second prototype (see Figure C.4 in [Appendix C](#)) is story focused. The ‘Hot’ tab on the main page shows the top story by default. Users can tap on an organisation icon or activity icon. Each organisation and activity has its page with specific information and stories.

The ‘Map’ tab shows the map of stories. Users can choose a geographical region of stories. Tapping on the area shows a list of stories and volunteer organisations. Users can go to a list of all stories organisations.

The organisation page allows users to add stories (by pressing on the ‘+’ icon) and donate items.

The bar at the bottom of the screen has similar options to the first prototype (Main screen, 'Favourite', 'Messages', 'Me').

User Scenarios

Scenario A: Sean O'Malley using the first prototype (Map)

Sean wants to show gratitude to Jane, the co-volunteer he works with. Jane has worked in his organisation for a year, thus he decided to post a story about her contribution to the local community. He pushes the '+' button on the main page. On the new page, he chooses content (several photos and videos of Jane during the work) and taps the 'Ok' button. Then writes warm words about her and the story title and tap 'Ok'. On the last page he sees the resulting story and puts hashtags for the place, volunteer organisation and activity. When everything looks good, he pushes the 'Ok' button (see Figure D.1 in [Appendix D](#)).

Scenario B: Sean O'Malley using the second prototype (Stories)

Sean wants to post a story about Jane, the co-volunteer he works with. He taps on the 'Favourite' button on the main screen. He chooses his organisation from the list. On the organisation list he taps on the '+' to add a new story. On the new page, he chooses content (several photos and videos of Jane during the work) and taps the 'Ok' button. Then writes warm words about her and the story title and tap 'Ok'. On the last page he sees the resulting story and puts hashtags for the place, volunteer organisation and activity. When everything looks good, he pushes the 'Ok' button (see Figure D.2 in [Appendix D](#)).

Scenario C: Jake Smith using the first prototype (Map)

Jake wants to find an animal shelter which needs volunteer help. He opens the app and pushes on the 'Volunteer' tab on the main page. He sees all the volunteer organisations around him. It seems difficult to find - too many options. So, he chooses the appropriate type of volunteering: animals. There are just a couple of shelters around him. He pushes on the nearest and reads general information. It sounds like a nice cat shelter. Jake likes that it is nearby and he does not need to spend much time commuting. He pushes on the weekend activity - it suits him the best. He reads the task: it is just general cleaning and feeding cats. It is what he was looking for, so he pushed the 'Join' button (see Figure D.3 in [Appendix D](#)).

Scenario D: Jake Smith using the second prototype (Stories)

Jake wants to find an animal shelter which needs volunteer help. He opens the app and pushes on the 'Map' tab on the main page. He sees the map of stories. He pushes on his local area and sees a list of stories and volunteer organisations. There is no information on how far away organisations are in one list, so he pushes the 'All' link. He sees the list of all organisations in the area. It seems difficult to find - too many options. So, he chooses the appropriate type of volunteering: animals. There are just a couple of shelters around him. He clicks on the first one and reads general information. It sounds like a nice cat shelter. Jake likes that it is nearby and he does not need to spend much time commuting. He clicks on the weekend activity - it suits him the best. He reads the task: it is just general cleaning and feeding cats. It is what he was looking for, so he pushed the 'Join' button (see Figure D.4 in [Appendix D](#)).

Results

Based on the developed scenarios, we discovered that both prototypes have their advantages and disadvantages. While the first one is focused on the map – more functional, easier to find stories, organisations in a particular place – both organisation map and stories map are placed on the main page and equally accessible. At the same time, some organisations could have activities in different places. Thus, it could be worth considering transforming it into a map of volunteer activities.

The second prototype is focused on stories. It is more entertaining for users and could help for better coverage of stories. It might be more convenient for people who mostly use the application for consuming stories. However, it is more difficult to find suitable activities - there is no map option. To sum up, we decided to proceed with the first prototype.

Hi-Fi Prototype

What was learned

Lo-Fi design analysis

An analysis of our lo-fi design revealed a need for several features, including:

- A blend of the map feature.
- A section where users can browse through the spotlights without a map.
- The volunteer opportunities need to be more clearly labelled.
- A “Create a Profile” feature was added for vetting purposes.
- An option to donate physical items (like tools, objects, or food/item donations).

Scenarios

From the analysis of our scenarios, our group decided on some additional features that needed to be incorporated into our hi-fi design. These features included:

- An easy, quick to use map feature.
- A simple design layout for posting stories.
- An option to message the volunteer organisation for inquiries.
- The ability to apply for volunteer opportunities straight from the application.
- A tool to sort through the different types of activities available.

Final High-Fidelity Interactive Prototype Design

Getting started

When first navigating the application, we designed an easy to use interface for the homepage (see Figure E.20 in [Appendix E](#)) and for signing up with email, name, and a password to create an account (see Figure E.21 in [Appendix E](#)). Once users have created a profile, it will appear as the screen in Figure E.22 (see [Appendix E](#)), with options for contact and a way for the user to navigate through all of their applications, stories they have interacted with, and donations they have made.

Using the map

Identifying volunteer opportunities: Figures E.1 and E.2 (see [Appendix E](#)) depict the main map features. At the top, there are two options for browsing: one for looking at stories and the other for volunteering. When the user clicks on “Volunteer”, it will bring them to a new page where they can use the map to look at opportunities available by location (see Figure E.8 in [Appendix E](#)).

Browsing stories: From the main map feature in Figure E.1 (see [Appendix E](#)), users can alternatively click on the the “Story” icon to bring them to a new page for browsing spotlights. From here, users can click on these fire icons to bring them closer to the general location and closer to the stories that were posted in these locations, for ease of browsing (see Figures E.2 and E.3 in [Appendix E](#)).

Spotlight feature

Once a user has clicked on an area, they can either browse the stories from the map or use an alternate list version as seen in Figure E.4 (see [Appendix E](#))

List feature: Stories will be presented by pictures (see Figure E.4 in [Appendix E](#)). Users can scroll through these pictures. Clicking on a picture will bring them to the full volunteer spotlight, pictured in Figure E.5 (see [Appendix E](#)). From there, the user can “like”, “comment”, or “share”.

Map feature: In Figure E.3 (see [Appendix E](#)), a similar interface is available. On this page, the stories are represented on the maps. Users can click on a story to bring them to the same spotlight page (see Figure E.5 in [Appendix E](#)).

Posting spotlights

On the organisations’ profiles, the option to post a picture is available through the “+” icon (see Figure E.2 in [Appendix E](#)). By clicking on this icon, users can select a cover image for their story (see Figure E.6 in [Appendix E](#)), then include the content for their spotlight (see Figure E.7 in [Appendix E](#)), then apply filters (see Figure E.9 in [Appendix E](#)), and then selecting hashtags and activities (see Figure E.10 in [Appendix E](#)). Once the user has finished, they can click the “Ok” icon, which will publish the spotlight (see Figure E.5 in [Appendix E](#)).

Browsing volunteer opportunities

Casual users will be able to explore potential volunteer opportunities through the map feature (see Figure E.8 in [Appendix E](#)). This page has a search bar and a filter at the top right. From this page, users can click on the various icons and browse through listings of volunteer opportunities. Selecting an activity will bring them to the listing page (see Figure E.13 in [Appendix E](#)), where they will be able to learn more about the activity and the organisation. From this page, users can also be linked to the organisation’s information page, which displays general information about the organisation’s volunteer opportunities (see Figure E.14 in [Appendix E](#)).

Applying for volunteer activities

Potential volunteers can apply for opportunities through two ways: from the listing page itself, where they can select the “Join” button (see Figure E.13 in [Appendix E](#)) and from the organisation’s information page, where they can select the “Apply” button at the bottom (see Figure E.14 in [Appendix E](#)). Both of these interfaces will submit the users’ basic information to the organisations.

Users can then browse through all of their applications by returning to the list version of the opportunities listing page (see Figure E.12 in [Appendix E](#)) and selecting “Applied” at the top. This button will redirect users to the list of opportunities they have already applied to entitled “My Activities” (see Figure E.12 in [Appendix E](#)). Once an application is submitted, users will receive a message like in Figure E.15 (see [Appendix E](#)).

Contacting the volunteer organisations

Users have several ways to communicate with organisations. From a listing (see Figure E.13 in [Appendix E](#)) or from the organisation’s main page (see Figure E.14 in [Appendix E](#)), a user can select the “Contact” button on the bottom left. These interfaces will direct users to the same contact page seen in Figure E.16 (see [Appendix E](#)), with several options like email, phone, and online message. The “Online Message” option works as built-in online messaging system.

The option for users to browse current and past chats is available by selecting the “Message” icon on the bottom right of their home screen (see Figure E.1 in [Appendix E](#)). This will take users to the screen in Figure E.17 (see [Appendix E](#)).

Making a donation

For users that are too busy but would still like to contribute, a feature has been added for them to make item donations. From the organisation's main page (see Figure E.14 in [Appendix E](#)), they can select the "Donate" option at the bottom right. This will take them to the donation page (see Figure E.18 in [Appendix E](#)), where they can browse through the lists of items that the particular organisation needs.

Evaluation

User evaluation: Cognitive Walkthrough

Cognitive Walkthrough is a theoretical usability-inspection method, which can be used to critique and identify problems of web platform navigation (Blackmon et al., 2002). According to The International Design Foundation (2022), Cognitive walkthroughs are conducted to check the usability of a product by evaluating if a new user can easily carry out tasks within a given system. It is an extremely cost-effective and fast to carry out task-specific approach to usability evaluation. We employed Cognitive Walkthrough for conducting user evaluation to our ‘Volunteer Spotlight’ application owing to these advantages.

To conduct a Cognitive Walkthrough, user tasks were defined and these tasks were divided into simple processes to follow. The user tasks were a blend of our User Scenarios and additional tasks to cover all the major features of the app. The following tasks were covered for the cognitive walkthrough:

1. *Task 1:* Open the Volunteer Spotlight app on your phone and look through it for a story of your interest
2. *Task 2:* Sign-up for volunteering with a category (Animal Shelter) and organisation of your choice.
3. *Task 3:* Post a volunteer story.
4. *Task 4:* Make a donation to an organisation of your choice.

Click paths were listed to guide the assessors through the application to complete the given tasks. Each group member played the role of an assessor with the user personas at hand. Following Blackmon et al. (2002) recommendations, four questions were used by the assessors:

- Will the user try and achieve the right outcome?
- Will the user notice that the correct action is available to them?
- Will the user associate the correct action with the outcome they expect to achieve?
- If the correct action is performed, will the user see that progress is being made towards their intended outcome?

Four assessors involved in the Cognitive Walkthrough performed each process in the given task and answered the four questions while completing the tasks. They recorded the problematic steps and issues in the process and these issues were discussed as a group (see Figure F.1 in [Appendix F](#)) to prioritise the issues for future improvement.

Results of the evaluation

Following are the key findings from the Cognitive Walkthrough test:

- The ‘Stories’ button on the ‘Dublin Stories’ screen was difficult to find. The participants felt that the users may not notice that the correct action is available to them and associate the correct action with the outcome they expect to achieve.
- No option to make monetary donations. Participants felt that users who wish to make donations in cash will not be able to do so. The participants found that the users will not notice that the correct action is available to them and that the users will not associate the correct action with the outcome they expect to achieve.
- Navigating to the Home screen was difficult. Although the participants could complete the tasks, they found it difficult to navigate back to the Home screen and felt that it would be a time consuming task for the users to navigate to the Main/Home screen from their current screen.

Recommendations

Following are the design recommendations for future development of the interface to resolve the problems that were discovered during the evaluation stage:

- Labelling unfamiliar icons. Using alternative text or labels to identify unfamiliar icons and clickable elements will help in improving its readability.
- Adding an option to make Monetary donations in the 'Donations' screen. Users who wish to make donations in cash will be able to make a quick cash transfer online.
- Adding a 'Home' icon to navigate to the Home or Main screen of the app. This will help users navigate back to the main screen and hence reduce the time consumed in navigation.

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Appendix A – Questionnaire and Personas

Figure A.1: Questionnaire. The consent form and example of questions.

User Centered Design Project

Consent Form

User Centered Design Project

Fair Processing Statement

Participation data is being collected as part of a research project concerned with volunteering. The study is being conducted by students of User Centered Design at University College Dublin as part of our design project. The data you supply will be de-identified and will be stored on a Google Drive file hosted by UCD and only accessed by authorised personnel involved with this project. The information will be retained by UCD and will only be used for the purposes of research and audit. By supplying this information, you are consenting to the university storing your data for these purposes. The information will be processed by UCD and the researchers in accordance with the provisions of the Data Protection Act (1998) and the General Data Protection Regulation (2016).

Statements of Consent

I agree to take part in this study.

I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time without giving any reason. If I withdraw during the experiment, the data will be deleted and removed from the study.

I understand that my personal data will be processed for the purposes detailed above in accordance with the Data Protection Act (1998) and the General Data Protection Regulation (2016).

Questionnaire

Are you interested in volunteering? *

- Yes
 No

Have you volunteered in the past? *

- Yes
 No

What types of organizations have you been involved with

- Volunteering to work with animals
 Community projects (working with children, elderly, LGBTQ+ organizations etc)
 Sports volunteering
 Medical (hospitals, doctor's offices, etc)
 Environment groups
 Church/religious organizations
 Other: _____

If you have not volunteered in the past, would you be interested in volunteering in the future?

- Yes
 No
 Not applicable

Figure A.2: Part 1 of Persona A (Sean O'Malley), including basic description.

Figure A.3: Part 2 of Persona A (Sean O'Malley), including motivations and painpoints.

Figure A.4: Part 1 of Persona B (Jake Smith), including basic description.

Figure A.5: Part 2 of Persona B (Jake Smith), including motivations and painpoints.

Appendix B – Competitive Audit, User Journey Map and Problem Tree

Figure B.1: Blue Ocean Strategy (Competitive Audit)

Blue Ocean Strategy & Design Concepts

Volunteer Ireland

'Volunteer Ireland', caters to people interested in volunteering. The competitor speaks about its services, app features, by sharing stories, recruiting, training and support centres.

Humans of New York

'Humans of New York' caters to social media users worldwide by posting stories, showing gratitude with a consistent theme which looks appealing.

VolunteerMatch

'VolunteerMatch', a platform to promote voluntary activities by posting volunteer requirements. It has various categories such as animals, art, culture and tech.

Insight

Compared to other volunteer platforms, we decided to let users can show gratitude towards volunteers by stories. Creating a map to show stories and find suitable volunteers organisations more easily.

Design Concepts

We decided to design a mobile application where people can read inspiring volunteer stories and information about volunteer organisations.

The platform map shows organisations, activities and stories. Users can choose suitable opportunities and communicate with host organisations.

By spreading (posting, liking and sharing) volunteer stories, both organisations and users show gratitude for volunteers and their work and gain positive effects for themselves.

Figure B.2: User Journey Map

Figure B.3: Problem Tree

Appendix C – Lo-Fi Prototypes

Figure C.1: Ideas generated during the session

Figure C.2: Categorized ideas

Figure C.3: Lo-fi 1 'Map'

Figure C.4: Lo-fi 2 'Stories'

Appendix D – User Scenarios

Figure D.1: Scenario A for Lo-Fi 1 and Persona A (Sean O'Malley)

Figure D.2: Scenario B for Lo-Fi 2 and Persona A (Sean O'Malley)

Figure D.3: Scenario C for Lo-Fi 1 and Persona B (Jake Smith)

Figure D.4: Scenario D for Lo-Fi 2 and Persona B (Jake Smith)

Appendix E – Final High-Fidelity Interactive Prototype Design

Figure E.1: Map interface main menu.

Figure E.2: Map interface for volunteer stories, with the option to switch to the volunteer activity map at the top.

Figure E.3: More localised view of the map for volunteer stories, with the search option (“Magnifying Glass” icon) and the option to switch to list view (“Four Squares” icon) available in the top right corner.

Figure E.4: List view of the volunteer spotlight stories with options for filtering at the top and in the top right corner.

Figure E.5: Spotlight story interface, with interactions available on the right side of the screen (“Share”, “Comment”, “Like”, and “Favorite” icons)

Figure E.6: Interface for posting volunteer spotlight stories (Part 1).

Figure E.7: Interface for posting volunteer spotlight stories (Part 2).

Figure E.8: Map interface for volunteer opportunities, with icons for selecting activities and tools to refine searches.

Figure E.9: Interface for posting volunteer spotlight stories (Part 3).

Figure E.10: Interface for posting volunteer spotlight stories (Part 4).

Figure E. 11: A list view of all available volunteer opportunities in the selected area.

Figure E.12: List of volunteer activities users can browse and apply for.

Figure E.13: Volunteer activity available for users, with detailed description of the activity and options to contact the organisation and apply for the opportunity.

Figure E.14: Main page for volunteer organisations, with detailed contact information and available volunteer opportunities.

Figure E.15: Confirmation for a volunteer activity application.

Figure E.16: The contact interface for users to get in touch with volunteer organisations.

Figure E.17: Chat interface.

Figure E.18: Donation interface, with item donations. Users can choose self-delivery or shipping the items, and can select dates for drop off.

Figure E.19: Confirmation page for donations.

Figure E.20: The main first page users encounter. Here, they are prompted to create an account.

Figure E.21: Interface for creating an account.

← Create your account

Name Input

Email Input

Phone number Input

Password Input

I agree with our [Terms and Conditions](#)

Sign in

Figure E.22: Account interface for users.

Appendix F – Cognitive Walkthrough

Figure F.1: Chart used for our Cognitive Walkthrough.

Cognitive Walkthrough					
Task	Click path	Question 1	Question 2	Question 3	Question 4
Write the task number and directions here.	Path to complete the task	Will the user try and achieve the right outcome? (Yes/No)	Will the user notice that the correct action is available to them? (Yes/No)	Will the user associate the correct action with the outcome they expect to achieve? (Yes/No)	If the correct action is performed, will the user see that progress is being made towards their intended outcome? (Yes/No)
Prompt 1: Open the Volunteer Spotlight app on your phone and look through it for a story of your interest	Click path1: Open the app > Tap on 'Story' on the Main page > Tap on 'Dublin' > Tap on 'Animal shelter' tab > Tap on 'Like', 'Share', 'Star', 'Comment' buttons	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
	Click path2: Tap on the 'Stories' button on the Dublin Stories screen(top right corner)	Yes	No	No	Yes
Prompt 2: Sign-up for volunteering with a category (Animal Shelter) and organisation of your choice.	Click path 1: From your current page (Animal shelter story), tap on the organisation name > Tap on 'Contact' button > Tap on 'Cancel' button to go back to the previous screen > Tap on 'Join' button > Tap on 'OK'	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
	Click path 2: Tap on 'Ireland' on the map > Choose 'Cat' icon(Animal shelter) > Choose the volunteer service(Cat helper) > Tap on 'Apply' button > Check for the volunteering task and organisation information and tap 'OK' > Check for the confirmation screen	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
	Click path 3: Tap on 'Volunteer' button on the Main screen(bottom on the screen) > Use the filters to look for an organisation > Tap on 'Cat helper' and 'Apply' button > Check for the volunteering task and organisation information and tap 'OK' > Check for the confirmation screen	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Prompt 3: Post a volunteer story.	From the main screen, push the "+" button on the bottom center of the screen > Choose photos or videos to post > press "I" button to choose text > Type the 'Story Title' and Type the 'Volunteer story' and tap on 'Ok' > Select the picture(s) to post and push 'Ok' button > Add the location, tag the volunteer organisation and add hashtags, tap 'Ok'	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Prompt 4: Make a donation to an organisation of your choice.	From the main screen, tap on 'Volunteer' tab > Tap on 'Ireland' on the map > Choose 'Cat' icon(Animal shelter) > Scroll to the end of the page > Tap on 'Donate' button > Choose the delivery Date(25th Saturday) and Delivery mode(Self drive) and tap 'Ok' > Check for all the information before submitting and tap on 'Yes' > Check for the confirmation screen and tap 'Return'	No	No	No	Yes